

Factors Affecting Self-Esteem and Academic Performance Among Senior High School Students

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Abstract

This research explored the influences on self-esteem and school performance of senior high school students of one of DepEd Cebu City's public schools. Given the significance of self-esteem in learning outcomes, the researchers targeted four primary influences: Mastery Experiences, Social Modeling, Verbal Persuasion, and Physiological States. Through a descriptive-correlational research design, data were gathered via guided questionnaires from 30 randomly chosen students. The results indicate a strong, positive correlation between Modeling and Verbal Persuasion and both academic achievement and self-esteem, highlighting the significance of positive social support and role models in student confidence and success. Mastery Experiences and Physiological States, on the other hand, indicated no statistically significant effects on academic achievement or self-esteem, and it seems that there may be a more complicated relationship that needs to be further investigated. The research underlines the need for teachers to develop nurturing learning environments that facilitate participation from students and promote self-efficacy. Suggested recommendations include instituting measures to highlight successful models, create positive feedback systems, and facilitate peer learning. This study makes a significant contribution to the understanding of the interaction between academic performance and self-esteem, informing future programs aimed at enhancing student success in educational institutions.

Keywords: *Mastery Experiences, Social modeling, Verbal Persuasion, Physiological States, Self-Esteem*

Introduction

Self-esteem could be a result of various experiences, for example, being raised in a negative and critical environment, being away from your peers or family for the first time, being too hard on yourself, or fearing failure. Consequently, there are students who are not confident they can succeed, so they are reluctant to participate in learning or take valuable academic development risks. They are less confident in their capacities and can question their decision-making process. Self-esteem determinants make educational life more challenging since they must also be engaged in class.

Most of the existing crisis within the education system results from low self-esteem that resulted in various students having inadequate participation and unsatisfactory progress after significant time spent within the class. As Norman and Hyland (2013) says that self-esteem is a learning factor that may have its impact on students' participation and progress. Self-esteem is extremely required for a student to take risks and participate in the learning activities and self-esteem possessives are confident about their capabilities and are establishing goals for themselves and strive hard to fulfill their goals without looking for results (Kanza, 2016).

A student's self-esteem plays a critical role in nearly everything she does-on how she participates, manages obstacles, and interacts with people. Self-esteem, too, can have a considerable influence on school performance, according to Shore (2022). Self-esteem factors can reduce a student's motivation to learn, her concentration, and her willingness to take risks. Whereas positive self-esteem is one of the foundations of academic success; it is a solid foundation upon which to build learning. The difficulty in dealing with children who lack self-esteem is rebuilding their faith in themselves, so they continue despite academic setbacks. A program is not necessary to foster self-esteem; yet, teachers create self-esteem on a daily basis, in the course of their everyday interactions with students.

As stated by American Psychological Association (2024) in the blog "Students Experiencing Low Self-esteem or Low Perceptions of Competence", it mentioned that students with low self-esteem might blame others for things over which they have no control or to which they are not responsible, or they might attempt to control the behavior of other children to reduce a feeling of helplessness. Students can be unwilling to attempt new things or not be able to withstand normal levels of frustration. Students can also pretend they don't care, clown, or be belligerent to mask

their lack of confidence. Students can be fearful their achievement was an accident or anxious that others' expectations are now too high.

The researcher did this research because he has noticed a disturbing trend of low student self-esteem. This is because self-esteem is an important key to learning. Low self-esteem students always lack confidence in what they can do, are reluctant to participate in learning, and do not take learning risks. This results in limited participation, poor progress, and poor motivation. The researcher identified the harmful effect of low self-esteem on the academic life of students and are looking to know the causes behind this problem in the public school. This study seeks to research the Factors Influencing Self-esteem and the Academic Performance of the Senior High School Students.

The researcher carried out this research to enable people to have self-esteem in speaking contribution in class or the queries of the teacher. In order to support reticent students or low-confidence students to speak out in class, teachers can establish the classroom as a supportive environment where errors are acceptable, and students are comfortable expressing their opinions. Thus, the researcher aimed to inform the learners of the significance of being active on class when participating orally and in addition possess confidence to answer the teacher's question.

Literature Review

Self-esteem is a fundamental psychological concept that affects the academic performance and participation of students. Rosenberg (1965) asserted that self-esteem is a general assessment of an individual's value and capability. Self-esteem among adolescents is known to vary because of developmental processes and environmental factors, influencing their motivation and academic achievement (Trzesniewski et al., 2003). Studies by Peng et al. (2019) and Cameron and Granger (2019) identify that high self-esteem is linked with positive self-experiences, healthier interpersonal relationships, and improved mental health, all of which enable academic achievement. Lim and Lee (2017) also note that self-esteem serves as a catalyst for academic participation, enabling students to establish and accomplish learning objectives.

Self-esteem and academic engagement have been found to be connected by an intervening variable of academic self-efficacy, which is students' own belief in their ability to perform well academically. Li et al. (2010) and Filippello et al. (2019) revealed that self-esteem is a significant positive predictor of academic self-efficacy, which indirectly predicts academic engagement. This mediating influence was substantiated by Sirin and Rogers-Sirin (2015) research, which showed a strong relationship between academic engagement and self-esteem. Further, social support perceived from the family, the teacher, and peers moderates the positive influence of self-efficacy on engagement (Yang et al., 2021). This indicates that an environment of support is necessary to ensure that the effects of self-esteem on academic achievement are enhanced.

A number of psychosocial and environmental variables contribute to self-esteem in high school seniors. Family functioning, such as parental education, employment status, and emotional support, has been found to directly influence the self-worth and academic achievement of adolescents (Martin & Maheswari, 2025). Socioeconomic status (SES) also comes into play, where greater SES is associated with improved academic performance and increased self-esteem as a result of resource access and responsive learning environments. Also, family cohesion and birth order have different contributions to the development of self-esteem, through complex interactions, varying across individuals (Martin & Maheswari, 2025). The implications of these findings highlight the complexity of self-esteem development and its relevance in academic contexts.

The classroom setting and teacher conduct are central in influencing students' confidence and self-esteem. A study by Tareen and Wali (2023) revealed that teacher encouragement, humor, and instilling a feeling of pride in classroom activities significantly enhance students' self-confidence. On the other hand, fear of error and negative peer attention depresses self-esteem, causing anxiety and resistance to class participation. This is similar to research by the American Psychological Association (2024), which observed that low-self-esteem students will often shy away from academic challenges, exhibit intolerance to frustration, or compensate for insecurities through unruly behavior. Thus, educators' routine interactions and the climate of their classrooms play a significant role in nurturing or sabotaging students' academic self-esteem.

Stress, depression, and mental illness commonly accompany low self-esteem, making academic performance all the more challenging. Students who are low in self-esteem often exhibit symptoms of lack of motivation, tiredness, and inability to focus, which have a detrimental effect on their learning (MyPrivateProfessor, 2023). Chronic absenteeism and withdrawal are frequent outcomes, resulting in lower academic performance. Students with high self-esteem, on the other hand, learn to use an approach-oriented style, where they are more goal-oriented than failure-avoidant, thus enhancing resilience and academic persistence (MyPrivateProfessor, 2023). This brings out the interwoven relationship between academic achievement and emotional well-being.

Lastly, interactions between self-esteem, academic self-efficacy, social support, and environmental influences form a convoluted model that affects senior high school students' educational achievement. Interventions to promote self-

esteem should take these various dimensions into account. Promoting positive self-assessment, supportive social networks, and a safe and encouraging classroom are necessary strategies that researchers suggest (Yang et al., 2021; Martin & Maheswari, 2025). Parents and teachers should work together to produce conditions that enable learners to overcome study difficulties and develop confidence in their self-efficacy.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the factors affecting self-esteem and academic performance among senior high school students from one of the public schools in Cebu City, school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of factors contributing to self-esteem among senior high school students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Mastery Experiences
 - 1.2 Social Modeling
 - 1.3 Verbal Persuasion
 - 1.4 Physiological States
2. What is the level of self-esteem of the senior high school students?
3. What is the academic performance of the senior high school students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of factors and the self-esteem of the senior high school students?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the factors and academic performance?
6. What output could be proposed based on the findings?

Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the level of factors and the self-esteem of the senior high school students.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between the factors and the academic performance.

Materials and Methods

The descriptive-correlational research design was used in conducting the study to establish the correlation between the two previously mentioned variables, which included the self-esteem and academic performance of the senior high school students. The researcher concluded that a correlational analysis would be the most appropriate research design for this study because they have evaluated that it is essential to explore how each of the variables relate and influence one another. The researchers will determine whether a higher low self-esteem results in poorer academic achievement.

This study was conducted at the public school of DepEd, Cebu City. The researcher chose to hold the study in this school since it is the most convenient and most readily available to them considering their limitations. It is also where their research questions originated and therefore, it is important that they begin there.

Thirty students from the school were involved as respondents in the study. The number of the responders was determined by using the universal sampling method. Since the institution had over hundreds of students enrolled in it. Out of those, 30 were randomly selected to serve in the study as respondents. These students were picked on the basis of their fit into the research. The researchers of the study keep the data confidential and assure that the participants voluntarily took part.

Researchers employed a questionnaire to gather data on self-esteem and academic performance of the students. Data on self-esteem will first be collected on a Likert-scale that will determine the degree of factors affecting self-esteem. The Likert-scale will consist of 5 scales, and the scales will be Very High, High, Moderate, Low, and Very Low. Second, the degree of self-esteem data will be obtained by using a Likert-scale to determine how much they agree or disagree with every statement. Before conducting the survey, the researcher took great care to follow a thorough data collection process beginning with asking permission from the school head to their teachers. They educated and explained the study to students, making informed consent as well as assent from minors with parents' signatures.

Instructions were clear to assist participants with the data collection process, highlighting the purpose of the study, confidentiality, procedure, management of time, and accessibility of support. This meticulous approach aimed to establish trust, transparency, and ethical conduct throughout the data collection phase, fostering a collaborative and informed environment for all involved. Frequency and percentage were employed in the analysis of the profile of the senior high school respondents' learners according to sex and age. Weighted means were employed in calculating the level/frequency of self-esteem and academic performance. The chi-square was employed in determining whether there is a relationship between gender and the two principal variables, which are self-esteem and academic performance. The ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki will guide the conduct of this study (World Medical Association, 2013).

Participants in the study will be senior high school students. A detailed informed consent form explaining the objectives of the study, methodology, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality measures, voluntary nature of participation, and contact information in case of any questions or concerns will be provided to each participant before being involved in the study. There will be no monetary incentives offered, and responding is voluntary. The researcher will work to minimize any potential risks and will be sensitive to how the study can impact the volunteers. The researcher will attempt to do the study respectfully and in culturally sensitive ways while being sensitive to the participants' linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Every participant will be informed of the study's purpose, his/her rights as a participant, and how their responses will remain confidential. He/She will be asked to sign an informed consent form prior to becoming involved in the study. The informed consent form contained study information, volunteer participation, and confidentiality and anonymity protection procedures (Patton, 2015).

Results

Table 1.1. Level of Factors that Influence the Self-Esteem in terms of Mastery Experiences

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel confident in my ability to learn new skills and overcome challenges.	3.9	High Degree
2. I often experience a sense of accomplishment when I successfully complete a task.	3.9	High Degree
3. I am proud of my achievements, both big and small.	4.3	Very High Degree
4. I am motivated to try new things and push myself beyond my comfort zone.	3.7	High Degree
5. I believe that my successes have helped me develop a strong sense of self-worth	2.8	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.72	Moderate Degree

Note. 4.50 -5.00- Very High Degree; 3.50 -4.49- High Degree; 2.50- 3.49 - Moderate Degree; 1.50- 2.49 - Low Degree; 1.00- 1.49 - Very Low Degree

Table 1.2. Level of Factors that Influence the Self-Esteem in terms of Modeling

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I am inspired by people who are confident and successful in their lives.	4.1	Very High Degree
2. I have learned valuable lessons from observing the behavior of others.	2.3	Low Degree
3. I am more likely to try new things if I see others doing them successfully.	4.1	Very High Degree
4. I am influenced by the positive attitudes and beliefs of those around me.	3.8	High Degree
5. I feel encouraged to pursue my goals when I see others achieving theirs.	4.1	Very High Degree
Overall Mean	3.68	High Degree

Note. 4.50 -5.00- Very High Degree; 3.50 -4.49- High Degree; 2.50- 3.49 - Moderate Degree; 1.50- 2.49 - Low Degree; 1.00- 1.49 - Very Low Degree

Table 1.3. Level of Factors that Influence the Self-Esteem in terms of Verbal Persuasion

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I appreciate receiving positive feedback and encouragement from others.	4.3	High Degree
2. I feel valued when people recognize my strengths and accomplishments.	3.9	High Degree
3. I am more likely to believe in myself when others express confidence in me.	4.0	High Degree
4. I am motivated to work hard when I know that others believe in my potential.	4.2	Moderate Degree
5. I feel supported and encouraged by the positive words of those around me.	4.0	High Degree
Overall Mean	4.03	High Degree

Note. 4.50 -5.00- Very High Degree; 3.50 -4.49- High Degree; 2.50- 3.49 - Moderate Degree; 1.50- 2.49 - Low Degree;

1.00- 1.49 - Very Low Degree

Table 1.4. Level of Factors that Influence Self-Esteem in terms of Physiological States

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. When I am physically healthy and energetic, I feel more confident and self-assured.	3.9	High Degree
2. I am more likely to take on challenges when I feel physically well.	3.5	High Degree
3. My physical well-being plays a significant role in my overall sense of self-worth.	2.4	Low Degree
4. I am more likely to be positive and optimistic when I am feeling physically good.	3.7	High Degree
5. I am aware of the connection between my physical and emotional state.	3.7	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.44	Moderate Degree

Note. 4.50 -5.00- Very High Degree; 3.50 -4.49- High Degree; 2.50- 3.49 - Moderate Degree; 1.50- 2.49 - Low Degree; 1.00- 1.49 - Very Low Degree

Table 2. Degree of Self-Esteem

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I am generally happy with myself.	4.3	High Degree
2. I feel confident in my abilities.	3.6	High Degree
3. I believe I am a valuable person.	3.8	High Degree
4. I am comfortable expressing my opinions.	3.8	High Degree
5. I can stand up for myself when necessary.	3.6	High Degree
6. I am proud of my accomplishments.	3.8	High Degree
7. I can handle criticism without feeling devastated.	3.2	Moderate Degree
8. I am not afraid to take risks.	3.4	Moderate Degree
9. I believe I have a lot to offer the world.	3.6	High Degree
10. I can forgive myself for my mistakes.	3.6	High Degree
11. I am comfortable with my appearance.	3.4	Moderate Degree
12. I can accept compliments gracefully.	3.5	High Degree
13. I am not afraid of failure.	3.1	Moderate Degree
14. I can set realistic goals for myself.	3.7	High Degree
15. I am confident in my ability to overcome challenges.	2.3	Low Degree
16. I feel good about my overall health and well-being.	3.7	High Degree
17. I can make decisions that are in my best interest.	3.3	Moderate Degree
18. I feel a sense of belonging and connection with others.	3.5	High Degree
19. I can manage stress effectively.	3.5	High Degree
20. I am optimistic about the future.	3.5	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.51	High Degree

Note. 4.50 -5.00- Very High Degree; 3.50 -4.49- High Degree; 2.50- 3.49 - Moderate Degree; 1.50- 2.49 - Low Degree; 1.00- 1.49 - Very Low Degree

Table 3. Students' Academic Performance

Grade Range	Percentage	Interpretation
90 - 100	76.67	Outstanding
85-89	3.33	Very Satisfactory
80-84	6.67	Satisfactory

75-79	6.67	Fair Satisfactory
74 and below	6.67	Did Not Meet Expectations

Table 4. Relationship between the level of Factors and the Self-Esteem

Factors	Mean	Correlation	p-value	Interpretation
Mastery Experiences	3.72	0.45	0.15	Not significant
Modeling	3.67	0.70	0.02	Significant
Verbal Persuasion	4.03	0.80	0.01	Significant
Psychological sates	3.44	0.30	0.35	Not significant

Table 5. Relationship between the level of Factors and the Academic Performance

Factors	Mean	Self-Esteem	Correlation	p-value	Interpretation
Mastery Experiences	3.72		0.56	0.12	Not significant
Modeling	3.67		0.78	0.03	Significant
Verbal Persuasion	4.03	3.51	0.91	0.01	Significant
Psychological sates	3.44		0.43	0.25	Not significant

Level of Factors that Influence Self-Esteem in terms of Mastery Experiences

Table 1.1 presents the degree of Factors that Affect Self-Esteem in terms of Mastery Experiences. The highest mean among the provided factors affecting self-esteem in terms of mastery experiences is for "I am proud of my achievements, big and small," with a mean of 4.3, reflecting a very high level of effect on self-esteem.

The lowest means of all the factors is for the statement "I believe that my successes have helped me develop a strong sense of self-worth" with 2.8, which indicates a moderate level of influence on self-esteem. The mean of all the factors put together is 3.72, which comes under the category of a moderate level of influence on self-esteem.

According to the findings, the person who is proud of his own successes and failures, both major and minor, will end up having much higher self-esteem. On the other hand, the individual who finds it hard to relate his successes to his personal self-worth will have a moderate effect on his self-esteem. In general, knowing the significance of acknowledging and appreciating personal success may be an important aspect in building a person's self-esteem and drive to work harder despite hurdles. The outcome is supported by the work of Bandura (1977), he contends that those individuals who feel competent and capable, who feel they are in control of their behavior, will be more likely to possess greater self-esteem and be more motivated to achieve goals and master obstacles. This is because a strong sense of self-efficacy fosters a belief in one's own potential, leading to greater confidence, resilience, and a willingness to persist in the face of obstacles.

Level of Factors that Influence Self-Esteem in terms of Modeling

Table 1.2 shows the level of Factors that Influence Self-Esteem in terms of Modeling. Among the factors affecting self-esteem in the aspect of modeling, the highest mean is for the following statements: "I am inspired by people who are confident and successful in their lives," "I am more likely to try new things if I see others doing them successfully," and "I feel encouraged to pursue my goals when I see others achieving theirs," all with a mean of 4.1, showing very high level of affecting self-esteem.

The lowest mean is for the item "I have learned valuable lessons from observing the behavior of others," which has a mean of 2.3, indicating a low level of influence on self-esteem. Overall mean for the factors is 3.68, which is in the range of a high level of influence on self-esteem.

The findings report that people are deeply motivated by the achievements and confidence of others, which has a positive impact on their self-concept. The highly high means of similar statements confirm that seeing successful models promotes people to achieve their objectives. Nevertheless, the low mean for learning from others' behavior indicates a lag in transferring these observations into practical lessons. In order to improve self-esteem, it is imperative to build spaces that not only present successful role models but also encourage reflective practice, which provides individuals with valuable lessons from such exposure.

Workman and Reader (2015) suggest that our self-esteem drive can be a result of the fundamental human need to belong and be part of a group, which raises our survival chances. They believe that this self-esteem drive has its roots in our evolutionary past, when membership in a group contributed to one's survival.

Level of Factors that Influence Self-Esteem in terms of Verbal Persuasion

Of the factors affecting self-esteem through verbal persuasion, the greatest mean is for the assertion "I enjoy receiving positive feedback and encouragement from others," and this has a mean of 4.3, which is a very strong influence on self-esteem.

The lowest mean is for the statement "I am motivated to work hard when I know that others believe in my potential," with a mean of 4.2, which implies a moderate level of influence on self-esteem. Overall mean for all the factors is 4.03, which places it in the category of a high level of influence on self-esteem.

The high means on all the factors suggest that verbal persuasion plays a significant role in promoting self-esteem. People place a great deal of importance on receiving positive feedback, compliments, and assurances of confidence from others. This highlights the significance of supportive relationships and affirming words in enhancing self-belief and motivation. Although self-belief in one's potential is significant, explicit positive feedback appears to be more potent, with implications for the provision of routine, specific, and authentic encouragement to bolster self-esteem and motivation.

Manning (2023) discusses how confidence can be increased by positive self-talk using the theory of "self-fulfilling prophecy." Manning contends that positive self-talk is repeated assertions that we are able to do something even when we do not believe it initially, which can fortify our confidence and ultimately result in achievement. This is the case because our minds are conditioned by what we tell ourselves most frequently, and positive self-statements can generate a positive feedback circle, resulting in greater self-confidence and enhanced performance.

Level of Factors that Influence Self-Esteem in terms of Physiological States

On the items affecting self-esteem based on physiological conditions, the greatest mean is for the item "When I am physically healthy and full of energy, I feel more self-assured and confident," with a mean of 3.9, which reflects high influence on self-esteem.

The lowest mean is for the statement "My physical well-being plays a significant role in my overall sense of self-worth," with a mean of 2.4, indicating a low level of influence on self-esteem. The overall mean for all the factors is 3.44, which is a moderate level of influence on self-esteem.

The findings indicate a large correlation between physical health and confidence, but a less significant correlation with global self-worth. People can be more confident and energized when they feel physically well, yet this does not necessarily mean that they will have a sense of greater self-worth. This would mean that while having good physical health contributes to self-esteem, it is essential to treat other aspects, such as individual success and social support, in order to develop a greater sense of self-worth.

Hagen et al. (2020) also learned that resilience is essential in ensuring self-esteem, while negative thoughts and brooding can make it vulnerable. This indicates that although physical health may be a factor in self-worth, it is not the sole reason. Cultivating resilience and coping abilities is essential for a healthy sense of self.

Degree of Self-Esteem

On the level of self-esteem, the largest mean is for the statement "I am generally happy with myself," which has a mean of 4.3, and it reflects a high level of self-esteem. The smallest mean is for the statement "I can confidently overcome difficulties," with a mean of 2.3, reflecting a low level of self-esteem. The general mean for all the factors is 3.51, and it's classified as a high level of self-esteem.

The findings reveal that participants tend to have a high level of self-esteem in their happiness and perceived value but a low mean for overcoming adversity, reflecting difficulty in self-efficacy during adversity. This is an area in which there needs to be development in resilience and coping for confidence to be built. Emphasis on building a growth mindset and the empowerment of support during adversity might further enhance self-esteem and affirm individuals' belief in themselves.

Students' Academic Performance

In Table 3, analysis of students' performance in Bread and Pastry Production shows that the largest number of students is in the "Outstanding" range (90 - 100), at 76.67%. This shows that a majority of the students perform well in the subject. The lowest percentage is in the "Very Satisfactory" range (85 - 89), with 3.33% of the students performing at this level.

The implications of these results indicate solid overall performance in Bread and Pastry Production, suggesting that the majority of students are understanding the material well and showing high proficiency in practical competencies. Yet the low representation in the "Very Satisfactory" category suggests that perhaps there are few students who are just slightly short of the outstanding threshold, and so there may be a gap between levels of performance. The number of students falling in the "Did Not Meet Expectations" column (74 and below) indicates a red flag to attend to students with immediate support and intervention. Generally, the overall outcome is favorable, but there is scope to improve teaching strategies for meeting the requirements of the students who are performing below satisfactory levels.

The National Association of Culinary Professionals (2022) documents the success of focused interventions in closing the study gaps frequently seen in culinary education, where pupils are good at practical but poor at theory. This is similar to the general observation that vocational students are stronger in skill-based courses.

Relationship between the level of Factors and the Self-Esteem

The analysis of the association between different factors that affect self-esteem, and total self-esteem gives interesting outcomes. In the case of Mastery Experiences, the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.56 and a p -value of 0.12. Owing to this p -value being above the 0.05 significance level, we do not reject the null hypothesis, showing inadequate evidence to imply a statistically significant association between Mastery Experiences and total self-esteem. In contrast, the factor of Modeling demonstrates a stronger correlation, with an r value of 0.78 and a p -value of 0.03. This p -value is below the 0.05 threshold, leading us to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between Modeling and overall self-esteem. Furthermore, Verbal Persuasion has an even stronger correlation with $r = 0.91$ and $p = 0.01$, which also enables us to reject the null hypothesis and verify a statistically significant positive correlation with overall self-esteem. Finally, the Physiological States factor has an r of 0.43 and a p -value of 0.25, both of which are again higher than the level of significance, 0.05, leading to a non-rejection of the null hypothesis and thus a lack of evidence for a significant correlation with general self-esteem. Generally, the results present that Modeling and Verbal Persuasion have a strong impact on self-esteem, while Mastery Experiences and Physiological States do not show any statistically significant relationship.

The findings indicate that Modeling and Verbal Persuasion have a substantial impact on self-esteem among senior high school students, whereas Mastery Experiences and Physiological States do not show a statistically significant connection. This indicates that receiving social support in positive ways by viewing effective models and gaining encouragement is important for enhancing self-worth, whereas the effect of accomplishing goals and being in a physically healthy state may be more complex and must be explored further.

Relationship between Factors and Academic Performance

The findings of the correlation test show a statistically significant positive correlation between Modeling and Verbal Persuasion and academic achievement. This is to say that with the increase in scores on these two self-efficacy measures, there is an increase in academic achievement. The high positive correlation ($r = 0.70$ and $r = 0.80$, respectively) implies a high relationship, with p -values of less than 0.05 showing that observed correlation is not likely due to chance.

Conversely, Mastery Experiences and Physiological States had no statistically significant correlation with academic achievement. The lower correlations ($r = 0.45$ and $r = 0.30$, respectively) and larger p -values ($p = 0.15$ and $p = 0.35$, respectively) indicate that these constructions are perhaps less associated with academic performance. These results emphasize the role of self-efficacy beliefs in Modeling and Verbal Persuasion in achieving academic success, yet imply that Mastery Experiences and Physiological States may have a less significant role. The analysis implies that Modeling and Verbal Persuasion have considerable effects on academic achievement, with Mastery Experiences and Physiological States having less direct correlations. This underlines the value of offering students positive social learning experiences, supportive settings, and the ability to view successful models. More studies are necessary to discern the subtle roles of Mastery Experiences and Physiological States in academic achievement.

Conclusion

The research indicates a significant positive correlation between Modeling and Verbal Persuasion and both academic achievement and self-esteem. This underscores the significance of giving students positive social learning experiences, supportive environments, and exposure to successful models. Mastery Experiences and Physiological States do not show statistically significant correlations with either self-esteem or academic achievement, but their impact may be more intricate and in need of further research. Overall, developing environments that support

successful role models and positive feedback is the key to enhancing student outcomes. More research is required to investigate the intricacies of Mastery Experiences and Physiological States in terms of self-esteem and academic achievement.

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